

EOSC Coordination Day Report

28 - 29 November 2019, Budapest

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November 2019 saw 30 EOSC-related projects come together for two days of discussions on how best they can collaborate in order to ensure a smooth implementation of key aspects of the EOSC. Organised by the EOSCsecretariat.eu project, the meeting saw agreement on a number of actions to bring projects closer together and foster the inclusive and collaborative nature of the EOSC. The meeting also followed up on actions agreed at the first [EOSC Concertation meeting](#) organised by European Commission in September 2019.

Four new EOSC Interest Groups (IGs)

With 60 participants at the meeting, discussion focused on how best projects can come together and, where possible, align work and share results with the short and long-term objectives of the EOSC in mind.

Through a series of interactive sessions and taking into consideration a broad spectrum of viewpoints, it was agreed that the set-up of Interest Groups on EOSC priority topics would be an effective way for projects to contribute to the work of the EOSC EB WGs.

As a starting point it was agreed that 4 Interest Groups will be set up in early 2020:

1. **Service Onboarding & Catalogues of services and research results** (1 interest group with different subtopics)
2. **Researcher Engagement and Use cases**
3. **EOSC Federating Core**
4. **EOSC Glossary**

The Interest Group model is based on the model used by RDA with a collaborative **public and open collaborative virtual space** where the members can discuss, share documents and structure their collaboration. The EOSC Secretariat will set up the underlying platform to support the interest groups.

The Interest Groups are open to all members of EOSC-related projects, no limit in the number of participants from a single project is envisaged. Private area of discussion can be implemented upon request..

The “allprojects” mailing list

The EOSC Secretariat will also create and manage a new mailing list made up of 2 representatives from each EOSC-related project. This will be used to communicate updates on the current and future IGs (allprojects@eosccsecretariat.eu). It will also be used by EOSCsecretariat.eu to communicate relevant updates to the EOSC projects and vice-versa. EOSCsecretariat.eu will also forward requests and information from and to the EOSC EB and its WGs.

Up to 2 members are included in the list (the Project Coordinator plus an appointed person). The projects representatives are invited to share the relevant information and requests within the project consortium. Any new EOSC-related projects wanting to join should send an email to info@eosccsecretariat.eu. The info@eosccsecretariat.eu email address can also be used to request changes in the mailing list representatives.

Breakout sessions agreed actions

User Engagement and Use Cases

Session Chair: Andreas Rauber (UNIVIE)

ACTION	WHO	Due date	Note
collect list of people willing to work on researcher engagement for mailing list set up collaborative space (on EOSCSecretariat.eu website), open to all	Emma Lazzeri Sara Garavelli	Next week By early 2020	
collecting outputs documenting researchers needs	All via mail then via collaborative space	1 month for first and then ongoing	
Provide a template for registering planned events on researcher engagement (for needs/feedback on services/NOT marketing selling or pure awareness raising) - Collecting list of events based on template - Collect results from events (researcher needs, feedback on services, ...)	TU Wien All Event organisers	Between now and Jan Jan - ongoing Ongoing	
Discuss / agree how this information will feed into WGs	TU Wien + all WG coordinators Including liaison with projects	March onwards	
Collecting contact names of projects (incl. short description)	All (via webform or wiki)	by end Dec (pre-populate from SIP)	for the overall collaboration action (not only related to this group)

Catalogues of services and research results

Session Chair: Paolo Manghi (CNR)

Points of actions agreed during the breakout session.

- It's not only about services, catalogues are needed on different fronts: metadata formats, scientific products (e.g., OpenAIRE Graph), data sources, and services (e.g., Marketplace)
 - Identify use-cases for each of the catalogues
- select the catalogues that should be part of the Federated Core
- ensure mechanisms to have feedback about the existing work and existing experiences in order to feedback to this work
- interoperability of catalogues
- how to ensure the sustainability of these catalogues

Roadmap:

- One pager online with a person that is in charge for the page
- Entry point for the material already produced by the projects, the tools and the tools that we need to before Christmas)
- Meeting before February

Onboarding

Session Chair: Owen Appleton (EGI)

Interest Group set up (one collaborative environment with subgroups). The main actions identified are:

- Identification of the challenges of onboarding in a service/data catalogue (not necessarily the central catalogue). These challenges may include: Training material to maturity of services/TRL, interoperability, duplications/PIDs, data onboarding - legal/ethical restrictions.
- Sharing of current best practices
- Understanding of the WG plans on these topics to synch
- Face to Face meetings to be organised.

It was suggested in this session to have a unique Interest Group for onboarding and catalogue of services as most of the people are involved in the same discussion. Clearly, the topics will be treated as 2 separate subtopics. This decision was endorsed by the full group in the wrap up session.

Federating Core

Session Chair: Paolo Manghi (CNR)

Interest Group objectives:

- Understand what has been done to date in order to metabolise what the FC will do.
 - Encourage stronger liaison between projects on topic.
 - Agree on FC terminology
 - Reach consensus on FC definition and components.
 - Understand future & sustainability of FC components
 - Provide a combined response to the EOSC-Hub working draft position paper on FC.

Agreed actions:

- We agree that the FC is the minimum set of “enabling” services, the question is to decide what they enable as they de facto will define the EOSC and its capabilities (it cannot simply be a service-oriented infrastructure)
- The FC should start small/conservative; further extensions may be considered if and when services joining the EOSC will become essential to EOSC, therefore part of the FC (e.g., preservation services)
- We want to produce a paper on the EOSC federating core and we make an official doc - the doc remains open but we should reach an endorsement by February

List of projects attending the EOSC Coordination Day

Project Acronym	Project Name	Website
AGINFRA PLUS	Accelerating user-driven e-infrastructure innovation in Food Agriculture	https://plus.aginfra.eu/
ARCHIVER	Archiving and Preservation for Research Environments	www.archiver-project.eu
BE OPEN	European forum and oBsErVatory for OPEN science in transport	https://beopen-project.eu
CatRIS	Catalogue of Research Infrastructure Services	https://project.catris.eu
COS4CLOUD	Co-designed Citizen Observatories Services for the EOS-Cloud	https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu
DARE	Delivering Agile Research Excellence on European e-Infrastructures	project-dare.eu
e-IRGSP6	e-Infrastructure Reflection Group Support Programme	e-irgsp6.e-irg.eu
ENVRI-FAIR	ENVironmental Research Infrastructures building Fair services Accessible for society, Innovation and Research	envri.eu/home-envri-fair
EOSC Enhance	Enhancing portals and thematic clouds	https://www.eosc-portal.eu/enhance
EOSC-Hub	Integrating and managing services for the European Open Science Cloud	www.eosc-hub.eu
EOSC-Life	Providing an open collaborative space for digital biology in Europe	www.eosc-life.eu
EOSC-Nordic		www.eosc-nordic.eu
EOSC-Pillar	Coordination and Harmonisation of National Initiatives, Infrastructures and Data services in Central and Western Europe	www.eosc-pillar.eu
EOSC-Synergy	European Open Science Cloud - Expanding Capacities by building Capabilities	www.eosc-synergy.eu

ESCAPE	European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle physics ESFRI research infrastructures	www.projectescape.eu
FAIR4Health	Improving Health Research in EU through FAIR Data	www.fair4health.eu
FAIRplus	FAIRplus	https://fairplus-project.eu
FAIRsFAIR	Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe	https://www.fairsfair.eu
FREYA	Connected Open Identifiers for Discovery, Access and Use of Research Resources	www.project-freya.eu
GN4-3	Horizon 2020: H2020-SGA-INFRA-GEANT-201Topic [b] Increase of Long-Term Backbone Capacity	www.geant.org
NI4OS	National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe	https://ni4os.eu
OCRE	Access to Commercial Services Through the EOSC-hub	www.ocre-project.eu
OpenAIRE-Advance	OpenAIRE Advancing Open Scholarship	www.openaire.eu
PaNOSC	Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud	https://www.panosc.eu
PRIMAGE	PRedictive In-silico Multiscale Analytics to support cancer personalized diaGnosis and prognosis, Empowered by imaging biomarkers	www.primageproject.eu
RDA Europe 4.0	Research Data Alliance	www.rd-alliance.org
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud	https://sshopencloud.eu
TRIPLE	Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked interdisciplinary Exploration	https://www.gotriple.eu